
Classroom Climate in Geometry Education

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SUMMARY

Existing Knowledge:

1. Classroom social climate significantly influences students' academic performance, engagement, and attitudes.
2. Prior research on classroom climate primarily focuses on secondary-level education or specific aspects of the environment.
3. Elementary students' perceptions of classroom climate have been understudied, particularly in mathematics settings like geometry.

New Insights:

1. Students predominantly perceive geometry lessons as teacher-centered, with frontal teaching methods and minimal peer interaction.
2. While classroom environments were orderly and goal-oriented, participatory learning and discovery methods were underutilized.
3. Participant-produced drawings provide rich, student-centered insights into psychosocial classroom climates.

Putting Research into Practice:

1. Training programs for teachers should emphasize student-centered, activity-based, and discovery learning strategies in geometry.
2. Teachers can utilize student drawings as a feedback tool to understand and improve classroom dynamics.
3. Incorporating diverse teaching tools and methods can enhance student engagement and collaborative learning in geometry lessons.

Keywords:

Geometry lessons, classroom social climate, elementary education, teaching methods, student perceptions, participatory drawings

Reference:

Kuzle, A. (2022). Elementary school children's perceptions of geometry classroom as a psychosocial learning environment: An analysis of participant-produced drawings. *Learning Environments Research*, 26, 379-399. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-022-09430-0>

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